

Infrared and Raman spectra of *N*-(substituted-phenyl)-2,2,2-trichloroacetamides

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Several substituted amides of configuration $X_yC_6H_{5-y}NHCOC_2Cl_3$, where $X = H, CH_3$ or NO_2 and $y = 1$ or 2 have been synthesised, and their infrared and Raman spectra measured. *N*-(Phenyl)-2,2,2-trichloroacetamide shows a strong C=O absorption at 1695 cm^{-1} , while that of other substituted-phenyl trichloroacetamides varies in the range $1695\text{--}1735\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The NH frequency for the parent compound, is at 3310 cm^{-1} , while that for others varies in the range $3270\text{--}3430\text{ cm}^{-1}$. C=O and NH frequencies for the amides of configuration $X_yC_6H_{5-y}NHCOR$ (where $R = CH_2Cl, CCl_3$ and CH_3) have also been compared. The infrared frequencies of various *para*-substituted amides in dilute chloroform have been examined for comparison. The intercorrelations of infrared C=O and NH frequencies and $\nu(^{35}Cl\text{ NQR})$ frequencies of *N*-(substituted-phenyl)-2,2,2-trichloroacetamides have also been attempted.

Amides are represented by the general structure $R^1-CO-NX-R^2$, where $X = H, OH, NR_2^3, COR^3, R^3$, and $R^1, R^2, R^3 = H$, alkyl or aryl group. Amides are of fundamental chemical interest as conjugation between nitrogen lone pair electrons and the carbonyl π -bond results in distinctive physical and chemical properties^{1,2}. Addition of a third hetero atom either α or β to the amino nitrogen of the amide group as in hydroxamic acids, *N*-halo compounds and hydrazides, increases their chemical complexity, which has required the advent of modern physical techniques to unravel. There are several reports on IR and Raman spectra

of anilines and amides, but there is not much work on *N*-substituted-amides³. We report herein IR and Raman spectra of a number of *N*-(substituted-phenyl)-2,2,2-trichloroacetamides.

Results and Discussion

Infrared and Raman frequencies of *N*-substituted-phenyl acetanilides measured in the present investigation and related compounds from literature are shown in Tables 1-6 and Figs. 1-3.

Fig. 1. Line diagram for variation of $\nu_{C=O}$ and ν_{NH} with substitution (⊗) CH_3 , (○) CH_2Cl , (Δ) CCl_3

Table 1. Infrared and Raman frequencies (cm^{-1}) of amides of configuration $X_yC_6H_{5-y}NHCOCCL_3$ with X_y

H		2-CH ₃		3-CH ₃		4-CH ₃		2,3-(CH ₃) ₂	
IR	Raman	IR	Raman	IR	Raman	IR	Raman	IR	Raman
436s	436m	448s	403m	435m	412m	505s	412m	565s	426vs
460m	511m	540m	425s	550m	438m	650s	438s	635s	485m
571s	524m	585s	452s	570s	520m	715m	503m	665m	500m
640s	818m	620s	514m	665s	573m	790m	512m	705m	537m
680s	1009m	685s	542m	685s	661m	815vs	641s	772vs	560s
742vs	1252s	725s	588m	775s	732m	880vs	700m	815vs	638m
820vs	1537s	765s	615s	820vs	769m	1248m	796m	840s	665s
878s	1610s	835vs	673m	850vs	796s	1405m	814s	920m	708m
968m	1700s	890s	702m	945m	990m	1515m	881s	1065m	770s
1035m	3325m	1040m	721m	1235m	1002s	1540m	1046m	1220s	803s
1075m	3340m	1115m	760m	1260m	1272vs	1600s	1090m	1265m	813m
1200s		1255s	803s	1300m	1299s	1695vs	1181m	1495s	1094s
1248s		1290m	889m	1450m	1550m	3300s	1244s	1520s	1163s
1315m		1460s	957m	1550vs	1595vs		1296s	1720vs	1217s
1375s		1480m	1040m	1695vs	1690m		1326s	3310s	1272vs
1454s		1520vs	1115m	3290s	3286m		1520m		1385m
1530s		1585m	1160s		3400m		1542s		1494m
1600s		1705vs	1212m				1610vs		1517m
1695vs		2930m	1250s				1690m		1588m
1710m		3330s	1382m						1602m
3310s			1513s						1697m
			1575m						3218m
			1700m						
			1740m						
			2979s						
2,4-(CH ₃) ₂		2,5-(CH ₃) ₂		2,6-(CH ₃) ₂		3,4-(CH ₃) ₂		3,5-(CH ₃) ₂	
IR	Raman	IR	Raman	IR	Raman	IR	Raman	IR	Raman
420m	430m	420m	429vs	420m	430s	440s	431s	420s	430vs
450s	450m	448s	452s	515m	482m	475s	463m	440s	535m
505s	565m	585s	489m	528m	514m	515m	505m	546m	662m
550s	680m	635s	561m	548m	526s	567s	557m	720m	691m
565s	700m	690m	592m	638s	549m	665s	706s	820m	825m
610s	737m	720s	640m	660m	636m	715s	746s	848m	998s
678s	766m	822s	690m	680m	663m	800m	815m	895m	1237s
700vs	935m	838s	716m	710s	688m	825s	956m	1040m	1305s
720m	1180m	1125m	751s	775vs	710s	845s	1125m	1160m	1319m
740m	1209m	1230m	806s	825vs	780s	882s	1234m	1235s	1602m
800m	1270s	1260m	817s	880s	826s	955m	1254vs	1270m	1775s
825vs	1383m	1505vs	841s	1095m	875s	975m	1288m	1318m	
875vs	1455m	1700vs	872s	1220m	988m	1020m	1303s	1375vs	
935m	1521m	2920m	930m	1245m	1094s	1160m	1382m	1460vs	
965m	1614m	3305s	1125m	1248s	1166m	1238s	1413m	1510s	
978m	1696m		1157m	1265m	1193m	1253m	1537s	1540s	
1230s			1234m	1510vs	1242s	1300s	1595s	1650s	
1265s			1257m	1700vs	1266s	1375s	1611s	1680m	
1520vs			1299s	3285s	1377m	1460vs	1695s	3430s	
1610m			1378s		1384m	1510m			
1700vs			1500s		1506s	1535s			
1719m			1523m		1593s	1599s			
3295s			1628s		1695s	1700vs			
			1701s		2924s	3270m			
					3286s	3425s			

Table 2 Infrared and Raman frequencies (cm⁻¹) of amides of configuration X_yC₆H_{5-y}NHCOCCl₃ with X_y

H		2 Cl		3 Cl		4 Cl		2 3 Cl ₂	
IR	Raman								
436s	436m	453m	402m	442s	446s	435s	437s	458m	427s
460m	511m	468m	430s	567m	557m	508m	632m	553m	455s
571s	524m	576m	453m	603m	819m	646m	645m	599s	500m
640s	818m	602s	575m	663m	999s	661m	699m	673s	549m
680s	1009m	650m	679m	676m	1247s	765vs	746m	702m	807m
742vs	1252s	668s	834m	769vs	1278s	813m	887m	781s	820m
820vs	1537s	677s	1037s	824vs	1440m	834vs	1100s	800m	1061m
878s	1610s	749s	1134m	835s	1600s	888s	1121s	815s	1178m
968m	1700s	775m	1165m	879m		980m	1255s	830s	1206m
1035m	3325m	821s	1241s	924s		1018m	1288s	908m	1267m
1075m	3340m	1034m	1293s	1082m		1080m	1288	908	1267
1200s		1060m	1591s	1101m		1099s	1550	1051	1454
1248		1136	1655	1216		1183	1600s	1191s	1527
1315m		1165m	1705m	1253m		1216s	1690m	1306m	1582s
1375s		1184m		1285m		1255s		1419s	1732m
1454s		1244s		1431vs		1315s		1534s	
1530s		1300m		1531s		1408s		1599s	
1600s		1450m		1600s		1499s		1744s	
1695vs		1528s		1698vs		1544s		3370s	
1710m		1531s		3253s		1610s			
3310s		1604m				1709vs			
		1640m				3262s			
		1680s							
		1717vs							
		3275m							
		3364vs							
2 4 Cl ₂		2 5 Cl ₂		2 6 Cl ₂		3 4 Cl ₂		3 5 Cl ₂	
IR	Raman								
450m		445s	422s	412s	402m	442m	436m	426s	
555m		551m	454s	433m	423s	473m	577m	473m	
600s		602s	590m	475s	515m	578s	662s	686m	
675s		669s	702s	615m	523m	666s	782s	781m	
706m		673s	789s	680m	616m	785s	817s	996s	
775m		790m	1051s	701m	691m	818vs	844s	1215m	
814m		813s	1240s	720s	701m	879s	871m	1235s	
825s		836m	1270m	775s	771m	928m	947s	1233m	
880m		930m	1410s	790m	899m	1037s	984m	1269s	
925s		1053m	1522m	820m	1078m	1215m	1121m	1304s	
985s		1198m	1585s	895m	1163m	1249s	1218s	1406m	
1055m		1270m	1729m	1075m	1230m	1296m	1274m	1444s	
1145m		1417s		1100m	1263m	1389m	1381m	1542m	
1256s		1597s		1200m	1282m	1401m	1422s	1591s	
1352m		1650m		1225m	1580m	1483m	1453m	1707m	
1435m		1735s		1255s		1528s	1546m		
1525m		3364s		1275s		1596s	1603s		
1585m				1375m		1702s	1718s		
1642s				1440m		3250s	1733s		
1715s				1465m			3305s		
3325m				1510m					
				1570s					
				1705s					
				2925m					
				3270s					

Table 3. Infrared frequencies (cm^{-1}) of amides of configuration $X_y\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NHCOCCL}_3$ with X_y

H	2-NO ₂	3-NO ₂	4-NO ₂
436s	420s	420w	425s
460m	455m	530m	490s
511s	525m	565m	535m
524m	660s	665s	635m
560m	740s	735s	670s
640m	770m	765m	750vs
680s	815m	820s	765m
742s	1040m	860s	815s
820vs	1260m	890s	825m
878s	1320w	950m	855vs
910m	1340s	1000w	885s
968m	1510s	1220w	965s
1018w	1625s	1260m	1010w
1030w	1700m	1280m	1115m
1075m	1720s	1325m	1180m
1200s	3280w	1350s	1200m
1248s	3380s	1435s	1250s
1315m		1530s	1300m
1375s		1605m	1348s
1460vs		1620m	1410m
1525s		1700s	1505s
1600s		1710s	1548m
1695vs		3296s	1600s
1710m		3395w	1625m
3310s			1735s
3290s			3320s

Table 4. Infrared and Raman frequencies (cm^{-1}) of amides of configuration $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NHCOR}$ with R

CH ₃		CH ₂ Cl		CHCl ₂		CCl ₃	
IR	Raman	IR	Raman	IR	Raman	IR	Raman
415m	632m	415w	566m	430s	400w	436vs	436m
507m	665m	505s	616s	450s	500w	460m	511m
535s	759s	560s	715m	500w	548m	511s	524m
608s	850m	572m	751m	530m	600w	524m	818m
620m	1001m	618m	774s	560m	760m	560m	1009m
670m	1025s	693s	860s	665m	819m	640m	1537s
697s	1179m	725m	1006vs	685m	875s	680s	1610s
723s	1269s	752m	1032m	728m	987m	742vs	1700s
758s	1325s	860s	1092m	760s	1012s	820vs	3325m
820w	1377s	905s	1176s	818s	1042m	878s	3340m
842m	1507s	965s	1254s	850m	1187m	910m	
852m	1550m	1035m	1347s	975s	1247s	968m	
908s	1603s	1080m	1450m	1000w	1355vs	1018w	
963s	1674s	1175s	1499s	1030w	1568s	1030m	
985w	2836m	1198s	1561s	1075w	1611vs	1075m	
1000w	2928m	1200m	1604s	1175w	1686s	1200s	
1014m	3047m	1255m	1677m	1220s	3296w	1248s	
1042s	3127m	1295s	1691m	1245s	3340s	1300m	
1082s		1350m		1285m		1375s	
1162m		1380s		1302m		1460vs	
1182m		1410m		1320m		1525s	
1268s		1465m		1340s		1600s	
1306w		1500m		1380vs		1695vs	
1325s		1560s		1400w		1710m	
1380s		1605m		1450vs		3310s	
1460s		1680s		1500m			

1502s	1700m	1550s
1540w	3220m	1600m
1560m	3290s	1675m
1600s		1688s
1623w		3295m
1685s		3340s
1760w		3400s
3265m		
3305s		

Assignment of the frequencies to the various vibrational modes is similar to the ones described elsewhere for a general category of compounds under secondary amides^{1,4}. *N*-(Phenyl)-2,2,2-trichloroacetamide shows a very strong C=O absorption at 1695 cm^{-1} . This absorption frequency for other substituted-phenyltrichloroacetamides varies in the range 1695–1735 cm^{-1} , except for *N*-(3,5-dimethylphenyl)-2,2,2-trichloroacetamide (1650 cm^{-1}).

Table 5. Selected infrared frequencies (cm^{-1}) of amides of configuration $X_y\text{C}_6\text{H}_y\text{NHCOR}$ with X_y and R

X_y	R = CH ₃		CH ₂ Cl		CCl ₃	
	CO	NH	CO	NH	CO	NH
H	1670	3305	1690	3250	1695	3310
2-CH ₃	–	–	1714	3340	1705	3330
3-CH ₃	–	–	1694	3365	1695	3290
4-CH ₃	–	–	1704	3365	1695	3300
2,3-(CH ₃) ₂	–	–	1658	3290	1720	3310
2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	–	–	1665	3238	1700	3295
2,5-(CH ₃) ₂	–	–	1680	3268	1700	3305
2,6-(CH ₃) ₂	–	–	1668	3260	1700	3285
3,4-(CH ₃) ₂	–	–	1678	3300	1700	3270
3,5-(CH ₃) ₂	–	–	1665	3310	1650	3430
2,4,6-(CH ₃) ₃	–	–	1675	3200	–	–
2-Cl	1670	3305	1693	3323	1717	3364
3-Cl	1670	3300	1691	3238	1698	3253
4-Cl	1645	3260	1670	3235	1709	3262
2,3-Cl ₂	1672	3300	1696	3330	1744	3370
2,4-Cl ₂	1660	3420	1675	3250	1715	3325
2,5-Cl ₂	1665	3420	1698	3355	1735	3364
2,6-Cl ₂	1660	3230	1685	3210	1705	3270
3,4-Cl ₂	–	–	1675	3370	1702	3250
3,5-Cl ₂	1685	3310	1725	3305	–	–
2,4,6-Cl ₃	–	–	–	–	1660	3345
2-NO ₂	1698	3310	1710	3380	1700	3370
3-NO ₂	1688	3300	1705	3296	1670	3250
4-NO ₂	1688	3378	1735	3320	1670	3330

The NH absorption frequency for the parent compound, *N*-(phenyl)-2,2,2-trichloroacetamide is at 3310 cm^{-1} whereas for others it varies from 3270 to 3430 cm^{-1} . Comparison of C=O and NH frequencies for the amides of configuration $X_y\text{C}_6\text{H}_y\text{NHCOR}$ (where, R = CH₂Cl, CCl₃ and CH₃) are shown in Table 5 and Fig. 1. Comparison of infrared frequencies for various *para*-substituted amides in dilute chloroform is shown in Table 6. Further, the infrared carbonyl frequencies of *N*-(substituted-phenyl)-2,2,2-

Table 6. Infrared frequencies (in chloroform solutions) of amides of configuration 4- $\text{XC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NHCOR}$ with X and R

X	R = CH ₃		CH ₂ Cl		CH ₂ Br		CHCl ₂		CCl ₃	
	NH	CO	NH	CO	NH	CO	NH	CO	NH	CO
N(C ₂ H ₅)	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	3395	1670
OCH ₃	3440	1685	3400	1679	3395	1678	3410	1700	3415	1718
CH ₃	3435	1685	3398	1680	3395	1680	3408	1703	3414	1719
H	3435	1690	3398	1683	—	—	3408	1703	3414	1722
O	3435	1690	3398	1683	—	—	—	—	3409	1721
F	—	—	—	—	3392	1684	—	—	3413	1721
Cl	3435	1695	3395	1685	3392	1686	3408	1705	3413	1723
Br	3436	1694	3395	1685	3393	1685	3407	1705	3411	1723
I	3437	1696	—	—	3392	1685	—	—	3413	1724
COCH ₃	3431	1702	—	—	3388	1685	—	—	3409	1727
CHO	3432	1701	—	—	3390	1693	—	—	3407	1729
CN	3431	1705	—	—	3388	1692	—	—	3409	1729
NO ₂	3430	1711	3391	1700	3387	1697	3402	1717	3406	1730

 Fig. 2. Plot of $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ vs ν_{NH}

trichloroacetamides have been correlated with their infrared NH frequencies in Fig. 2. The correlation of C=O absorption frequencies with the corresponding ν (³⁵Cl NQR) has also been attempted in Fig. 3.

 Fig. 3. Plot of $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ vs ν (³⁵Cl NQR)

Experimental

The substituted-phenyltrichloroacetamides were prepared from aniline, trichloroacetic acid and phosphoryl chloride⁵ (Aldrich). The commercial anilines were purified by either double distillation or zone refining. The respective anilines were treated with a clear mixture of trichloroacetic acid and phosphoryl chloride with constant stirring. The mixture was slowly warmed to expel HCl. Excess phosphoryl chloride was hydrolysed by adding cold water dropwise under ice-cold conditions. HCl produced was removed by treating with excess 2*M* NaOH. The solids separated were washed with water and dried. The substituted-phenyltrichloroacetamide were recrystallised from

ethanol. Purity of the compounds was checked by elemental analysis (C, H and N).

The substituted amides prepared were, *N*-(phenyl)-2,2,2-trichloroacetamide (m.p. 83°), *N*-(2-methylphenyl)-2,2,2-trichloroacetamide (90°), *N*-(3-methylphenyl)-2,2,2-trichloroacetamide (98°), *N*-(4-methylphenyl)-2,2,2-trichloroacetamide (104°), *N*-(2,3-dimethylphenyl)-2,2,2-trichloroacetamide (91°), *N*-(2,4-dimethylphenyl)-2,2,2-trichloroacetamide (89°), *N*-(2,5-dimethylphenyl)-2,2,2-trichloroacetamide (72°), *N*-(2,6-dimethylphenyl)-2,2,2-trichloroacetamide (138°), *N*-(3,4-dimethylphenyl)-2,2,2-trichloroacetamide, *N*-(3,5-dimethylphenyl)-2,2,2-trichloroacetamide, *N*-(2-chlorophenyl)-2,2,2-trichloroacetamide, *N*-(3-chlorophenyl)-2,2,2-trichloroacetamide, *N*-(4-chlorophenyl)-2,2,2-trichloroacetamide, *N*-(2,3-dichlorophenyl)-2,2,2-trichloroacetamide, *N*-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)-2,2,2-trichloroacetamide, *N*-(2,5-dichlorophenyl)-2,2,2-trichloroacetamide, *N*-(2,6-dichlorophenyl)-2,2,2-trichloroacetamide, *N*-(3,4-dichlorophenyl)-2,2,2-trichloroacetamide, *N*-(3,5-dichlorophenyl)-2,2,2-trichloroacetamide, *N*-(2-nitrophenyl)-2,2,2-trichloroacetamide (60°), *N*-(3-nitrophenyl)-2,2,2-trichloroacetamide (100°) and *N*-(4-nitrophenyl)-2,2,2-trichloroacetamide (138°).

IR spectra were measured (nujol) on a NICOLET MAGNA-550 FT-IR spectrophotometer. The resolution was set to 1 cm^{-1} and the scanning range 400–4000 cm^{-1} . NaCl prism was used. Raman spectra were measured on a RAMANOR HG-25 laser Raman spectrometer (JOBIN-YVON, France). The resolution of the spectrometer was better than 0.5 cm^{-1} . The excitation source was a 4 W argon ion laser (Coherent, U.S.A.) and 488 nm line was selected. The spectra of anilides were recorded from their microcrystalline samples.

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